

Proposed Framework: Philippines Initiative Against Corruption (PIAC)

Version 1.1

By Jonelle Peter Muñoz

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17230441

September 30, 2025

Abstract

The Philippines Initiative Against Corruption (PIAC) is a citizen-driven framework to promote transparency and accountability in public infrastructure projects. It introduces a presumption of accountability for politicians, engineers and contractors involved in substandard or overpriced projects, while empowering citizens to report anomalies through social media. A centralized digital archive will support investigations and strengthen public oversight.

Core Principle

To raise the standard of infrastructure projects, the burden of proof that no irregularities exist shall rest jointly on the politician, the supervising engineer, and the contractor. They share accountability to demonstrate, with verifiable evidence, that the project was executed properly and in accordance with approved standards and budgets.

Every Filipino citizen may actively participate in monitoring and reporting anomalies in public projects through social media, particularly Facebook. Upload a post using a simple four-step format.

Step 1: Upload a Facebook Post

- Upload a clear photo of a project or contract with suspected irregularities (e.g., poor quality, incomplete, or overpriced construction).

Step 2: Standard Caption Format

- Name of Project and Location: _____
- Name of Politician Involved: _____
- Name of Contractor: _____
- Name of DPWH or LGU Engineer: _____

- Approved Budget: _____
- Estimated Kickback: _____ (Leave blank if unsure; engineers, architects, accountants, or other experts may provide input later. Ideally, an estimate from at least two independent professionals with five years of experience is required. *Licensed Civil Engineer and a Licensed Architect.*)
- Status of this Post: Unverified or Incomplete (by default, all posts are “UNVERIFIED” and “INCOMPLETE” until reviewed by an independent party).
 - *Independent Verification:* Posts may be verified by an independent party, such as but not limited to, NGOs, civil society organizations, universities, or professional associations with no conflict of interest with the project proponents. If formal verification is not possible, at minimum, one video or vlog showing the project in real time should accompany the report.

See Annex A for an example of the original Facebook post format.

Step 3: Dissemination

- Post the entry in at least three local Facebook groups to maximize community awareness. (Optional but ideal)
- If there is already an existing post, just add an additional comment or a photo of the project.
- Tag #KMJS or another independent anti-corruption group.

Step 4: Standardized Hashtag

- Use hashtag to help the newly formed Independent Commission for Infrastructure (ICI), Mayor’s for Good Governance (M4GG), Secretary Vince Dizon, and independent reputable organizations **to HELP document, report and monitor** infrastructure projects.
- **Format:** #ProvinceCityPIAC or #ProvinceMunicipalityPIAC
- **Example:** #BulacanHagonoyPIAC

Alternative Options for Concerned Citizens

- If afraid to post publicly for personal reasons, concerned Filipino citizens may post anonymously in community groups or secure channels. Anonymous posts can also be

politicized, so by default, all posts are marked as UNVERIFIED and INCOMPLETE unless VERIFIED or COMPLETED by an independent party.

- The politician, engineer or contractor involved, ideally, must publicly explain to defend their innocence. *Since corruption in the Philippines is systemic, we also need a systemic solution.*
- Confident individuals may directly **tag politicians, engineers and contractors** in their posts.
- An official Facebook group or website may be established by an Independent Commission for Infrastructures (ICI), Mayor's for Good Governance (M4GG), or other independent civil organization to centralize all reports for easier investigation and tracking.
 - Existing government institutions such as the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH), the Commission on Audit, the Ombudsman, and the Sandiganbayan are considered. However, over the past 30 years, the Philippines' score in Transparency International has been very poor. *If these institutions had done their jobs well, this Proposed Framework would not be necessary.*

This proposed framework does not rely on a few public officials or existing government institution. It relies on the collective vigilance of citizens and a clear shift of accountability to those entrusted with public funds.

Long-Term Plan

A dedicated PIAC website will eventually host all reported irregularities, filtered by province, city, politician, and contractor involved. This digital archive will support independent investigations and provide transparency to the public.

Tayo ay mag-bayanihan para sa Pilipinas laban sa kurapsyon.

Together, citizens and institutions can ensure that every peso of public funds is used properly and that corruption has no place in Philippine governance.

This framework constitutes an original proposal (Version 1.0). The four references cited below are provided for broader global context. Should evidence of a similar concept published prior to September 23, 2025 emerge, the reference list will be updated accordingly.

References

- Bauhr, M., & Grimes, M. (2013). Indignation or resignation: The implications of transparency for societal accountability. *Governance*, 27(2), 291–320. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gove.12033>
- Bertot, J. C., Jaeger, P. T., & Grimes, J. M. (2010). Using ICTs to create a culture of transparency: E-government and social media as openness and anti-corruption tools. *Government Information Quarterly*, 27(3), 264–271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2010.03.001>
- Delos Reyes, J. D. [Joselito D. Delos Reyes]. (n.d.). *Sampung palapag, 232 classrooms. Napakalaking paaralan. Libo-libong estudyante. Tatlong taon nang ginagawa. Ang contractor?* [Image attached] [Status update]. Facebook. <https://web.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=10239574178271622&set=a.10203995732112704>
- Kapuso Mo, Jessica Soho (KMJS). (2025, September 29). *Mga proyektong inuugnay kay Ako Bicol Rep. Zaldy Co mula sa mga ghost road sa Albay hanggang sa ₱245 milyong coliseum sa Catanduanes, inimbestigahan ng #KMJS...* [Video]. Facebook. <https://web.facebook.com/reel/1829066638493526>
- Olken, B. A. (2007). Monitoring corruption: Evidence from a field experiment in Indonesia. *Journal of Political Economy*, 115(2), 200–249. <https://doi.org/10.1086/517935>
- Participedia. (2019). *I Paid a Bribe: Participatory website to combat corruption in India* [Case]. Participedia. Retrieved from <https://participedia.net/case/5579>
- Presidential Communications Office. (2025, September 18). *President Marcos signs EO 94 creating independent commission for infrastructure*. Presidential Communications Office. Retrieved from https://pco.gov.ph/news_releases/president-marcos-signs-eo-94-creating-independent-commission-for-infrastructure/

Document History

- Version 1.0: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5526461

ANNEX A

Original simple post published on Facebook (September 23 to 24, 2025)

Proposal: Philippines Initiative Against Corruption

Both the politician and the contractor of substandard and overpriced projects are GUILTY UNLESS PROVEN INNOCENT. The burden of proof that there are no irregularities lies with the two of them.

All Filipino citizens can post in their Facebook account the following details.

- Step 1: Upload a picture of a project that looks substandard and overpriced.
- Step 2: Standard caption:
 - Name of Project and Location:
 - Name of Politician Involved:
 - Name of Contractor:
 - Approved Budget:
 - Estimated Kickback: Leave blank if unsure, so other civil engineers and experts can provide.
- Step 3: Post in at least three local Facebook groups. (Optional but ideal)
- Step 4: Use a standard hashtag to HELP the newly Independent Commission for Infrastructure, M4GG, and Secretary Dizon in their investigation through this standardized format.

Hashtag format: Name of province and city/municipality followed by the acronym PIAC.

Example: [#BulacanHagonoyPIAC](#)

A website can be created later to post all these irregularities. The website can filter by province or city, so the above hashtag is important.

If you are afraid to post publicly for personal reasons, you can upload it anonymously in some local Facebook groups. If you are confident, you can tag the politicians or contractors as well.

If an FB group will be formed by the independent commission or M4GG, you can post the project picture, caption and hashtag there.

"Either we accept deception as normal, or we try something new."

The corruption in the Philippines is systemic, so we need a systemic solution in which every Filipino can participate.

Bayanihan para sa Pilipinas kontra kurapsyon.

[#BayanihanParaSaPilipinas](#) [#ProvinceCityPIAC](#)

People's Initiative Against Corruption

Upload a Picture of a Substandard Project with the Following Caption:

Name of Project and Location:

Name of Politician Involved:

Name of Contractor:

Approved Budget:

Estimated Kickback: Leave blank if unsure,
so other civil engineers and experts can provide.

Use a standard hashtag to HELP the
newly independent commission, M4GG, and Secretary Dizon.

Hashtag format: Name of province and city/municipality
followed by the acronym PIAC. **Example:** #bulacanhagonoyPIAC

Image Source: Facebook Account of the author, 2025.

Note: The acronym *PIAC* may refer to either *Philippines Initiative Against Corruption* or *People's Initiative Against Corruption*. Both reflect the spirit of the framework: a citizen-driven movement for national accountability.

ANNEX B

Published on September 28, 2025

Questions to High-Ranking Public Officials, Lawmakers, and Public Policy Makers

1. What can you say about the Presumption of Accountability? The reverse of the Presumption of Innocence.

For example, when there is a collapsed bridge, a ghost project, or an unfinished project, who is the most accountable and guilty? Can we assume that politicians (such as the Local Chief Executive for LGU projects), the supervising LGU engineer, and the contractor are equally accountable and guilty for the failure to deliver the project?

For DPWH projects, would it instead be the highest District Engineer and District Representatives, along with the supervising DPWH engineer and contractor, who should be held accountable?

Presumption of Accountability:

In the context of public projects, the politician, engineer, and contractor responsible for substandard or overpriced work shall be considered accountable unless they can demonstrate otherwise. The burden of proof lies with them to show that the project was executed properly and without irregularities.

2. Can we apply the concept of prima facie evidence for the following?

- A project billboard picture only for ghost projects since there's no project to be audited. (Like the billboard found by trail riders in Cebu)
- A picture of an unfinished project posted by a citizen on social media. (Like the ten storey school project in Sampaloc Manila that cost 1.4 Billion.)

A project billboard refers to the project information board that contains the project name, location, budget or price, and other details.

For example, can a verified picture or video, once authenticated by an independent party, be used as strong prima facie evidence?

Prima facie evidence refers to evidence that, on its face ("at first sight"), is sufficient to establish a fact or raise a presumption unless it is disproved or rebutted.

3. "Corruption is systemic, and we need a systemic solution to solve the problem in which every Filipino can participate."

If you are the DPWH Secretary or the President of the Philippines, how will you solve the nationwide corruption problem systematically?

4. How important is the passage of the FOI Bill? Can the President veto the budget insertions of those senators and congressmen who will not vote in favor of the passage of the FOI Bill?

ANNEX C

First PIAC Post Published on September 28, 2025

Repost Author: Jonelle Peter Muñoz, caption adapted for PIAC format

Name of Project: Construction of Ten (10) Storey, 232 Classrooms School Building at Ramon Magsaysay High School

Location: Sampaloc, Manila

Name of Politician Involved: _____

Name of Contractor: St Timothy Construction Corp and D.C. (Unincorporated Joint Venture)

Name of DPWH or LGU Engineer: _____

Approved Budget: Php 1,398,211,635.44

Estimated Kickback: _____

Post Status: Unverified / Incomplete (Unless otherwise Verified or Completed by independent party)

Philippines Initiative Against Corruption

[#BayanihanParaSaPilipinas](#)

[#ProvinceCityPIAC](#)

[#ManilaSampalocPIAC](#)

Image Source: Joselito D. Delos Reyes, Facebook post, [Date of Post],

<https://web.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=10239574178271622&set=a.10203995732112704>

ANNEX D

Post Published on September 29, 2025

Repost Author: Jonelle Peter Muñoz, caption adapted for PIAC format

Name of Project: Construction of 6,000-seater Coliseum at Catanduanes State University

Location: Virac, Catanduanes

Name of Politician Involved: Zaldy Co of Ako Bicol Partylist

Name of Contractor: Hi-Tone Construction Company

Name of DPWH or LGU Engineer: _____

Approved Budget: Php98 Million (Phase 1) and Php245 Million (Phase 2)

Estimated Kickback: _____ (To be Computed by an Independent Licensed Civil Engineer or Architect)

Post Status: Incomplete Details (Unless otherwise Completed by Independent Party)

Video source: Kapuso Mo, Jessica Soho (KMJS Special Reports)

Philippines Initiative Against Corruption (PIAC)

[#BayanihanParaSaPilipinas](#)

[#ProvinceCityPIAC](#) or [#ProvinceMunicipalityPIAC](#)

[#CatanduanesViracPIAC](#)

Video Source: *Kapuso Mo, Jessica Soho (KMJS) Facebook page*, "MGA PROYEKTONG INUUGNAY KAY AKO BICOL REP. ZALDY CO MULA SA MGA GHOST ROAD..." [September 29, 2025], <https://web.facebook.com/reel/1829066638493526>

Keywords

Corruption, Philippines, Good Governance, Transparency, Accountability, Citizen Participation, Civic Engagement, Crowdsourcing, Public Procurement, Infrastructure Oversight, Social Media Activism, Digital Governance, E-Governance, Whistleblowing, Political Reform, Anti-Corruption Policy, Governance Innovation, Development Studies, Rule of Law, Systemic Corruption, Public Sector Reform, Community Monitoring, Public Accountability, Political Economy of Corruption, Collective Action against Corruption